

COMPOSITE AUTO BUMPER: DESIGN AND PROCESS EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

A thorough analysis of composite material systems is undertaken to produce a bumper beam which has optimized manufacturing performance. An optimized preform architecture is derived, based on through-the-thickness permeability, and properties. Coupled with the manufacturing process, material design is qualified through rigorous mechanical testing. Once completed, the mechanical properties of the material are implemented in the design of the composite bumper beam. Finite element methods are incorporated in the analysis of the beam, to monitor stress and strain response. Finally, a subroutine is developed which captures failure initiation within the bumper beam.

Keywords: bumper, finite element, permeability, SRIM

1. INTRODUCTION

Bumper beams are the backbone of the energy absorbing systems located both forward and aft on automobiles. The entire bumper system usually consists of an exterior fascia, the underlying structural member, and an energy management foam or hydraulic stroker system. Traditional automobile geometry entails a flat-faced bumper system, but with current trends of design and aerodynamic efficiency, the sweeping curves of the automobile must be embraced with equally stylish bumper systems. These requirements prohibit the straight, rolled steel bumper beams of past. A multi-staged stamping process may provide the required curvature, but each stage accrues cost. This manufacturing dilemma is resolved with conformable composite material, additionally achieving weight reduction. One possible composites solution is Structural Reaction Injection Molding (SRIM), wherein a dry bed of fiber bundles is draped to form (a preform), then reaction injection molded. Even though this manufacturing process offers flexibility in composites, a rigorous analytical approach is required to optimize the SRIM bumper beam.

The specific architecture of the reinforcing preform plays a crucial role in the molding and structural performance of an SRIM component. (Ref. 1). The reinforcement must allow the resin to be transferred through the part as evenly as possible, while fully penetrating the fiber bundles. The difficulty or ease with which a fluid can penetrate the reinforcement is referred to as the permeability of the material. The extent to which the matrix saturates the reinforcement is referred to as wet-out.

In this research effort, several materials were compared to the baseline properties of commercially available FABMAT™, which is a dry fiber preform consisting of a woven mat bonded to a chopped random mat. Because of the high volume productions, FABMAT™ is a relatively inexpensive supply of fibers, however fiber ratios and orientations are limited to those

provided by the manufacturer. Therefore, an engineering model of the functionality of fiber composites is designed for a specific application. The optimization of an SRIM reinforcement system depends on many parameters including: the proper ratio of fibers running the length of the beam to those running the width of the beam, weave type, reinforcement layer weight, fiber size, type of random mat, stitched or woven materials, part thickness, etc.

2. MATERIAL DESIGN

In order to establish a test program, an experimental design was established in which the parameters of interest were identified as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters Considered.

<u>Constants</u>	<u>Independent Variables</u>	<u>Dependent Variables</u>
Fiber Diameter	Textile Architecture	Material permeability
Sizing	Tow size and spacing	Material wet-out
Resin System	Fabric Weight	Structural properties
Molding Parameters		
-(injection rate, injection ports, mold temp)		
Fiber Weight Percent		
Fiber Orientation		

The dry preform consists of a bed of fiber bundles (woven or stitched), which can be stacked with alternating mats of random fibers which aid permeability. Specific fiber ratio (longitudinal to transverse) and fiber weight percentage were selected to limit the variability in the test matrix. Regularity of the ratio was achieved through selection of different tow weights and tow passes per inch. With dense mats (high tow passes per inch), fiber weight was kept constant by reducing the number of mats in a constant thickness. Alternatively, low density mats required multiple layers to maintain fiber weight. After an extensive material matrix was outlined, manufacturing constraints reduced the preform selection to 16 systems.

SRIM technology was implemented in the consolidation of fiber and resin. The two-fold process first heats and stamps a stack of fiber mats, which have been treated with a thermoplastic binder (used to maintain preform shape on cool-down). Next, the preform is transferred to another mold, where the resin is injected and allowed to cure. The components of the material systems, include fibers from Fiber Glass Industries and resin from The Dow Chemical Company. The E-Glass fibers were as reported isotropic, with the following modulus, Poissons' ratio, and specific gravity, respectively:

$$E_f = 68.95 \text{ GPa}, \nu_f = 0.24, g_f = 2.46$$

SPECTRIM MM310 resin was also reported isotropic, with the following properties:

$$E_m = 3.45 \text{ GPa}, \nu_m = 0.30, g_m = 1.19$$

3. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

3.1. Permeability Measurements

Permeability is a measure of how easily a given material can be penetrated by a fluid or gas. Z-permeability is defined as the resistance of a material to fluid flow perpendicular to the material plane. Similarly x-permeability and y-permeability correspond to flows in the 0 degree and 90 degree fiber directions respectively. The in-plane permeability of a given reinforcement is most closely associated with the overall mold fill pattern of a component utilizing that reinforcement, while the z-permeability tends to dominate the overall wet-out of the resulting component. Since component wet-out, not mold fill, is of primary concern for this research effort, permeability testing was performed in the z-direction.

The permeability of a given material is a function of the Darcy permeability (Ref. 2) and is defined as follows:

$$D = \frac{(\text{flow rate}) * (\text{viscosity}) * (\text{thickness})}{(\text{differential pressure}) * (\text{area})} \quad (1)$$

This permeability value is a function of the reinforcement alone, and not a function of the flow conditions. The flow medium used in testing is Terrasic 68, a turbine oil with a room temperature viscosity of approximately 134 cp. which resembles that of the liquid polyurethane injected into the actual bumper beam preforms. The z-permeability test fixture holds a sample disk of the material in a cylinder through which a viscous medium flows. The material sample is held between two porous plates, separated by a spacing ring, so that its thickness remains constant, independent of the flow rate. By carefully measuring the flow rate, pressure drop across the sample, sample thickness, and the viscosity of the flow medium, a value for the Darcy permeability of the material can be obtained.

3.2. Wet-out Measurements

The wet-out of a given part is a measure of how well the matrix system integrated itself with the preformed fiber reinforcement. This dependent variable is determined using immersion C-scan techniques. By measuring the amount by which the intensity of the sound wave is diminished as it passes through the part, the relative porosity of the part is obtained. If the part is poorly wet-out and there are many places where the matrix system did not penetrate the fiber bundles, the intensity of the sound wave is greatly decreased, due to the multitude of reflective surfaces. If the part is very well wet-out, there is only a minor reduction in the intensity of the sound wave. In order to provide a comparable base with which to compare C-scan readings, the gain was set such that 100% wet-out represents wet-out obtained when the signal is passed through water only.

3.3. Plaque Structure

The 16 material systems were formed by the SRIM process, into 635x635x6mm plaques. Generally, a 25mm border around the plaque was scrap, leaving a 610x610mm usable portion. Each plaque was C-Scanned for an initial quality assurance, then diamond cut to provide specimens for the structural database. The materials were subjected to several standardized tests (Ref. 3) to evaluate in-plane modulus and strength (tension, compression, flex, and shear), and void content.

3.4. Bumper Beam

For a bumper to qualify for use on U.S. vehicles, it must pass rigorous full scale testing (Ref. 4). Prior to the federal test, a screening of potential beams is performed, using a modified three point bend configuration, shown in Figure 1, with a plate driven into the face of the beam at static rates (0.21 mm/sec). This test was performed using an Instron 1127, while recording load and crosshead deflection data. Herein, reference to the bumper beam performance is based on the modified three point bend tests.

4. COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

Finite element analysis, FEA, is implemented to evaluate the mechanical response of the bumper beam subjected to static loading. Two commercial codes are utilized in the analysis: Patran II for element definition, and ABAQUS which provides the numerical computations. In addition, a failure subroutine was developed, which detects ply failure and progressively degrades the element stiffness of the laminate until ultimate failure occurs. All computations were performed on a CYBER.

Due to symmetry in the bumper, load, and boundary conditions, only one-half the beam was modeled with four noded shell elements with reduced integration and Gaussian quadrature, and five degrees of freedom per node (S4R5 in the ABAQUS element library). The completed

Figure 1. Modified three point bend for bumper beam testing.

model contains 1800 elements, and 2500 nodes. Nonlinear geometry option with incremental loading is selected for the analysis. The loading was simulated by driving a planar surface normal to the face of the beam. This corresponds to the loading of the beam in the Instron test machine. Load and deflection of the plate are recorded, and ply failure location is noted during the duration of the model run.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Permeability

Initial testing began with z-permeability measurements on a sample disc preform made with multiple plies. These tests produced several notable conclusions. First, a substantial decrease in permeability with increasing flow rate was observed. This decrease in permeability is attributed to a geometric change in the material as the various fiber bundles began to nest together with increased differential pressure across the specimen. Although the permeability of a material drops as the flow rate increases, this only holds true for the initial flow rate. Thereafter, if the flow rate is reduced and then increased, the permeability remains relatively constant, "remembering" the permeability at the higher flow rate.

These results are consistent with a permeability decrease due to increased fiber nesting under increased differential pressure. Another interesting phenomena is that several of the materials appear to be approaching a minimum value of permeability asymptotically as flow rate increases, thus a minimum "limit" value for the permeability of these reinforcement architectures can be set. In order to make the comparison consistent, the permeability of each material was recorded at the same differential pressure (1034 KPa).

A mathematical expression was utilized to predict the permeabilities of the reinforcement from their architecture. The equation calculates permeabilities using a relationship between the size and number of holes penetrating each layer and the total number of layers in a lay-up. The basic form of the equation (2) is given below:

$$P \propto \frac{\left[\frac{(\text{total fiber volume } \%)}{(\# \text{ of layers})} \right]^m}{\sum_1^{\# \text{ layers}} \left[\frac{(\text{layer volume } \%)}{(\text{pore fraction})(\text{avg pore size})^n} \right]} \quad (2)$$

where:

avg. pore size = average area of holes penetrating a given layer
 pore fraction = total area of pores per unit area of a given layer

The comparison between the experimental and theoretical permeabilities is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparison of experimental and theoretical permeabilities.

Figure 3. Wet-out/Permeability Curve.

5.2. Wet-out

Each viable plaque was inspected in an immersion C-scan and the overall plaque wet-out obtained. The results of the wet-out measurement were then plotted against the reinforcement permeability in Figure 3.

Correlation data represent plaques produced with reinforcement architectures currently used in production bumper beams, and were included in the plaque production and testing for comparison purposes. As illustrated, a distinct maximum wet-out value is obtained at a permeability of approximately four. There also appears to be a region of good wet-out at permeabilities greater than twenty. Conversely, permeabilities between seven and seventeen show very poor wet-out. The peak at a permeability of four could be due to a large differential pressure during molding that causes the resin to penetrate the fiber bundles. At permeabilities much lower than four, the resin may not be able to fully penetrate the reinforcement, causing a lowering of the wet-out. The local area of poor wet-out between 7 and 15 permeability may be an unstable flow region, causing increased porosity and thereby lowering the wet-out. The final wet-out region at permeabilities greater than 18 may be stable flow, but without enough differential pressure during molding to cause the resin to penetrate the fiber bundles, thus lowering the wet-out slightly. Further testing is required to validate these conclusions.

5.3. Plaque

Compression and shear data for the material systems are shown in Table 2. From the baseline FABMAT™, all systems have improved performance in the longitudinal properties, whereas transverse properties are reduced. This is due to a change in the fiber ratio in the 15 systems versus the FABMAT™. The change in ratio resulted from observations of the stress distribution in the bumper beam.

Table 2. In-plane properties from material systems.

Material Type	0° Compressive		90° Compressive		In-plane Shear	
	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
FABMAT™	15.03	219.95	15.58	207.54	2.84	73.78
M02	17.96	230.29	8.07	115.15	5.17	125.49
M04	25.30	467.48	14.62	195.82	NA	NA
M05	26.27	454.38	12.55	197.20	1.96	55.85
M06	28.82	NA	13.00	198.23	NA	NA
M07	21.68	302.00	8.69	166.86	3.79	119.28
M08	22.86	326.82	11.03	188.23	3.37	117.21
M09	22.96	265.46	12.20	189.61	3.80	112.39
M10	21.03	290.28	11.72	171.69	3.63	117.90
M11	23.22	324.93	12.14	190.30	3.94	122.73
M17	21.62	266.84	11.17	144.80	2.64	70.33
M18	23.93	372.67	14.00	179.27	2.93	84.81
M19	25.00	302.69	13.65	145.48	2.80	68.95
M20	23.58	266.84	14.00	152.38	2.70	63.43
M22	24.82	283.04	15.31	171.00	2.82	62.74
M26	32.68	469.55	20.48	227.50	2.96	55.16

The strengths vary greatly from one material system to another, indicating that the different layer types exhibit different failure modes. Further analysis is scheduled to more fully understand the failure modes of each different layer type.

Comparison of the experimental and predicted values of modulus are shown in Figure 4, where predicted values were calculated from micro-mechanics and rule of mixtures (Ref. 5,6). Most of the moduli measured are within 10% of the predicted values with a few exceptions. The modulus prediction of the 0/90 lay-ups tended to fall short, which may be due to inaccuracies in input transverse fiber stiffness. A majority of the 0° moduli fall within the same basic range of 20 to 25 GPa. This is expected since all the materials have the same fiber ratio and volume percentage.

Figure 4. 0° compression data.

5.4. Bumper Beam

Bumper beams were fabricated from a woven reinforcement continuous mat combination. The dashed curves in Figure 5 are the upper and lower bounds from a set of manufactured beams, tested with the modified three point configuration. With the experimental data of the plaque, mechanical properties were implemented in the definition of the bumper beam for finite element analysis.

From the load-deflection curve of Figure 5, FEA provides accurate response in comparison with the experimental data. The slope of the curve appears to have a piece wise linearity. The change in slope near the 48 KN load, is a result of the contact area of the flat plate with the bumper beam. Failure zones on the bumper beams were consistent from experiment to numerical predictions. Within the impact area of the bumper beam, a compressive stress state dominates the axial direction of the beam. As indicated in Figure 6, FEA predicts a highly directional stress state at the crest of the beam. From videotaped experiments, identical failure modes initiated directly beneath the center of the crosshead at the attached plate, shown in Figure 7.

Failure prediction was based upon a maximum strain criteria, scrutinized within individual plies. Catastrophic failure of the beam is not precisely predicted, but failure initiation is closely followed in the numerical analysis.

6. CONCLUSIONS

With the increasing attractiveness of composite systems to replace conventional homogeneous materials, traditional design sequences must be expanded. In the specific manufacturing process of SRIM, through the thickness permeability defines preforms which provide optimized properties. The initial testing demonstrates the successful application of the test equipment to determine the properties of interest. Results have revealed definite correlations between the geometry of a reinforcement, the z-permeability of that reinforcement and the overall wet-out and moduli of the resulting SRIM component. Utilizing the permeability measurements, a preform can be designed with optimized manufacturing and performance properties. This preform is then implemented in the design of an automobile bumper beam.

7. References

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Figure 5. Chord modulus curves for experimental and theoretical bumper beams. Each beam constructed from identical material system.

Figure 6. Axial stress distribution (MPa) from FEA. Stress state shown for outer ply.

Figure 7. Compression damage on face of bumper beam. Note injection sprue at center of beam.